

Potential Effects of Aqueous Plant Extracts against Hide Beetles, *Dermestes maculatus* (De Geer) Larvae Infesting Dried Fish

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Abstract

the research was carried out to determine the potential effect of aqueous extracts of five plants; *Balanite aegyptiaca* (L.), *Eugenia aromatica* (hook), *Piper guineense* (Schum and Thonn), *Occimum grastisimum* (L.) against 3rd instars larvae of *Dermestes maculatus* by topical application. The extracts were tested by application of 2.0μL solution to the dorsal surface of each 3rd instars larvae using micropipette at concentration of 2.00, 6.00, 10.00 and 20.0% of each plant extracts. Thirty (30) 3rd instars larvae were randomly selected treated at various concentration of each aqueous plant extract and the same number of 3rd instars were treated with distil water as control. Mortality was recorded at 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 7th day of post treatment periods. *O. grastisimum* recorded the highest larval mortality range from 30.00 -76.66%, followed by *P. guineense* (26.66 - 76.77%), *Ziziphus mauratunia* (33.33 - 66.66%), *Eugenia aromatica* (33.33-56.66%) and *B. aegyptiaca* (26.66 - 53.33%) with untreated control having lowest larval mortality of 20 00%. All the aqueous plant tested were reveled to caused significant (p<0.005) larval mortality when compared to untreated control groups. The result showed strong insecticidal activity, in control of larvae of *D. maculatus* infesting dried fish and can be recommended in prevention and control of *D. maculatus* infestation on dried fish.

Keywords: *Dermestes maculatus*, Larval-mortality, Plant extracts, Topical application,

1.0 Introduction

Dermestes maculatus (Degeer), commonly called Hide Beetle; is belong to the order Coleoptera and family Dermestidae it is one of the most destructive insect pests of stored smoked-dried fish in Nigeria [1]. *Dermestes maculatus* is responsible for extensive damage of dried fish during storage, transportation and marketing leading to enormous economic loss [2,3]. Tejumade [1] reported *D. maculate* account for about 71.5% of the observed dried fish infestation with substantial loss in dry weight of about 43-62.7% .

The control of these pests in Nigeria is primarily dependent upon repeated application of synthetic chemicals such as chloripyripos-methyl, permethrin, cypermetrin, Benzene hexachloride (BHC), and "Otapiapia" (locally formulated) onto fish carton [4]. Although many synthetic chemical

are effective the general use of such chemicals to protect stored fish infestation has been hampered by potential health hazard, high cost of purchase, lack of availability, illiteracy of fish handler for required chemical dosage and less susceptibility of *Dermestes* larvae [5,6]. The potential human health of such synthetic chemicals has attracted enormous attention of the scientific communities search for alternative pesticide to dried animals product by the use of botanical pesticide.

Botanical pesticide tends to have broad spectrum activity and relatively specific in their mode of action and easy to process and use [7]. To minimize use of synthetic pesticide, several plants extract have been reported as effective to *D. maculatus* on dried fish [8,9,10,11,12]. These extracts will provide a solution to the problem emanating from the use of synthetic chemicals. The present studies have been chosen to

investigate the effects of topical application of aqueous plant extracts against larvae of *Dermestes maculatus* infesting dried fish as an alternative strategy to synthetic chemicals.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area is Sokoto State and lies between latitudes 13°03'N and longitude 5°14'E. It is bordered by the republic of Niger at the North and locally bordered by Kebbi State at the West and Zamfara State at the East [13]. Sokoto is characterized by rainy seasons between mid-May to mid-October and dry season between late-October to late-April. The monthly average temperature and relative humidity varies from minimum of 20°C to maximum of 45°C and 55%-70% during the year [13].

2.2 Collection, Identification and Preparation of Plant Materials

Five samples of locally available plants were selected based on verbal information obtained from fish mongers for storing dried fishes and their insecticidal effects against other insect pest of stored products as reported by [14,9].

The sample of dried fruit *Piper guineensis* and *Eugenia aromatica* were obtained from Sokoto central market, while the leaves of *Balanite aegyptiaca*, *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Ziziphus mauratania* were obtained from their natural habitat around Dundaye area of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The plants were identified *in-situ* and authenticated in the Herbarium of Biological Sciences Department of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto with a voucher specimens number (UDUH/ANS/0221, 0223, 0238, 02447, 0258) and were documented.

Samples were shade dried in the entomology laboratory of Usmanu Danfodio University, Sokoto for two weeks, milled into fine powders using mortar and pestle, sieved with 0.2mm mesh size following the methods describe by [25,9,16]. Each plant powders were were put separately in a well labeled plastic container and placed in a cool dry place prior to use. The sample of conventional (cypermethrin) insecticide was purchased from Sokoto Central Market, kept in cool dry dark place, which serve as positive control.

2.3 Collection and disinfestations of dried fish

The dried fish sample of *Clarias gariepinus* were purchased from Sokoto Central Market, Sokoto and identified at the Department of fisheries, Usmanu Danfodio University, Sokoto. The fish samples were disinfected by heat treatment in the laboratory drying cabinet at 60°C for 1 hour and allowed to cool at room temperature, following the methods described by [17].

2.4 Collection of Hide Beetle and Managements of Stock Culture

Different stages of *Dermestes maculatus* were obtained from naturally infested fish collected from Sokoto Central Market fish stalls and were identified morphologically using taxonomic keys [18]; Shiv et al., 2018. The species were confirmed at the Museum of Natural History Department of Biological Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Several male and females of *D. maculatus* were obtained and kept in transparent plastic containers (19.0cm height and 21.2cm in diameter) fed with dried fish. The containers were covered with Muslin cloth and tight with rubber band. Wet cotton wool was supplied in each jar to provide water requirements for oviposition as suggested by [19]. The pupae stage were picked up and transferred in to separate containers to obtained newly emerged adult, which were used for regular supply of larvae for the experiment. The culture was kept under laboratory condition at temperatures of 30°C ±2 °C and 65% ±5% relative humidity for the regular supply of newly emerged larvae.

2.5 Preparation of Crude extract (aqueous)

Crude extract (aqueous) were prepared from the powdered plant material using the following procedure: One hundred gram from each plant powder was weighed and soaked in 100ml of distilled water in a separate plastic container and was kept for 24hrs at room temperature. The mixtures were filtered separately using fine muslin cloth to remove debris. Each filtrate was then evaporated in a drying cabinet overnight at 40°C following the method of [9, 20].

2.6 Effect of topical application of aqueous plant extracts against *D. maculatus* larvae

Effect of aqueous plant extract against *D. maculatus* larvae by tropical treatment was

conducted according to method of [21]. 2µl of each plant extract at 2.0, 6, 10, and 20.00% concentration were applied to the dorsal surface of the thorax of third instars larvae of *D. maculatus*. Thirty (30) larvae were treated at each dose. In addition, the same numbers of larvae were treated with distill water as control. After treatment larvae were transferred to plastic container containing 20g of dried disinfected fish which was covered with muslin cloth and tied with rubber band. Mortality was recorded at 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 7th days of post treatment and percentage mortality was calculated.

2.7 Data analysis

Data obtained were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using General Linear Model [22]. Means found to be significant were separated using Duncan multiple range test at 5% level of significant ($p < 0.05$).

3.0 Results

3.1 Effects of topical applications of Aqueous Plant Extracts on *D. maculatus* Larvae

The potential effect of five plants aqueous extract tested on *D. maculatus* larvae by topical application are presented in Table 1, the toxicity effect of the aqueous extracts was observed to be increased with increasing concentration and exposure period. The larval mortality observed between the 2,6,10, and 20 % concentrations of *P. guineense* extracts and 20% concentration of *O. gratisimum* was significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared with untreated control at 1st day and 2nd day of exposure, all the tested plants at 20% concentration and 10% concentration of *P. guineense* and *B. aegyptiaca* was found to be significantly ($p < 0.05$) effective in controlling the larvae compared with control. The *P. guineense* and *B. aegyptiaca* aqueous extracts remain

effective throughout the trial period 3rd and 7th day exposure. After seven days of exposure *O. gratisimum* and *P. guineense* showed greater efficacy compared with others tested plants extracts. At the 20% concentration *P. guineense* and *O. gratisimum* had highest mortality to *D. maculatus* larvae (76.77%) followed by *Z. mauratania*, *E. aromatica* and *B. aegyptiaca* with 66.66%, 56.66% and 53.33% of *D. maculatus* larval mortality. The percentage mortality of larvae from untreated control was 20.00%.

4.0 Discussion

The result obtained from the study on the potential effects of aqueous plant extracts of tested plant on *D. maculatus* larvae by topical application revealed that all the tested plant extract was found to be effective against larval stages of *D. maculatus*. The result showed that the higher concentration of both treatments was more effective compared to the other test concentration and untreated control. These results are in agreement with many researchers on the use of plant material against larval stage of *D. maculatus* [10,14,23,24,25]. Medeiros et al. [27] reported the effectiveness of aqueous extracts of clove against larvae of *Aedes aegyptii* and *Anopheles darling*. Chapagain and Wiesman [26] also reported the effectiveness of aqueous extracts of *Balanite aegyptiaca* against larvae of *Culex pipiens* mosquitoes. The effectiveness of these tested extracts may be attributed to the presence of different bioactive compound in different plant extracts. These secondary compounds (phytochemicals) such as terpenoid, Alkaloid, glycoside, phenols and tannins found in some plant materials or extract makes it to have some insecticidal properties and its exposure can affect insect nerve axon and synapses muscles, respiration, hormonal balance, reproduction and reproduction behavior [27].

Table 1: Effects of topical application of aqueous Plant Extracts on Mortality of *D. maculatus* (Deg.) Larvae

Name of plant	Concentration (%)	Mean number of <i>D. maculatus</i> larvae mortality± SE				Mortality (%)
		Period of exposure (days)				
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	7 th	
<i>P. guineense</i>	20	6.33±1.20 ^b	6.66±0.88 ^b	7.00±1.00 ^b	7.66±0.33 ^{ab}	76.77
	10	5.0±0.57 ^{bc}	5.33±0.33 ^{bcd}	5.66±0.33 ^{bc}	6.66±0.33 ^{bc}	66.66
	6	4.33±0.33 ^{bcd}	4.66±0.33 ^{bcd}	5.00±0.57 ^{bcd}	5.66±0.88 ^{bcd}	56.66
	2	1.33±0.66 ^{ef}	2.00±0.57 ^{fg}	2.66±1.20 ^{de}	2.66±1.20 ^{de}	26.66
<i>B. aegyptiaca</i>	20	3.00±1.15 ^{cde}	3.66±0.33 ^{defg}	4.0±0.57 ^{cde}	5.33±0.88 ^{bcd}	53.33
	10	2.33±0.33 ^{def}	3.66±1.45 ^{defg}	4.00±0.57 ^{cde}	4.33±1.45 ^{cde}	43.33
	6	2.00±0.57 ^{def}	3.33±0.57 ^{fg}	3.66±1.45 ^{cde}	4.33±0.66 ^{cde}	43.33
	2	1.00±1.00 ^{ef}	1.00±1.00 ^l	1.66±1.66 ^c	2.66±1.66 ^{de}	26.66
<i>E. aromatica</i>	20	2.33±0.88 ^{def}	3.67±0.88 ^{defg}	5.00±0.00 ^{bcd}	5.66±0.33 ^{bcd}	56.66
	10	2.33±1.45 ^{def}	3.00±1.15 ^{efgh}	3.33±1.20 ^{cde}	4.00±1.52 ^{cde}	40.00
	6	1.33±0.66 ^{ef}	1.33±0.57 ^{hi}	3.33±0.57 ^{cde}	3.66±1.42 ^{cde}	36.00
	2	0.00±0.00 ^f	1.00±0.00 ⁱ	2.00±1.45 ^e	3.33±1.76 ^{de}	33.33
<i>O. gratisimum</i>	20	5.33±0.88 ^{bc}	6.00±0.57 ^{bc}	7.33±0.33 ^b	7.60±0.66 ^{ab}	76.66
	10	2.00±2.57 ^{def}	2.00±0.57 ^{fg}	3.66±0.66 ^{cde}	4.66±0.33 ^{bcd}	46.60
	6	1.66±0.33 ^{ef}	2.00±0.57 ^{fg}	3.00±0.57 ^{cde}	4.00±0.57 ^{cde}	40.00
	2	1.33±0.88 ^{ef}	1.66±0.88 ^{ghi}	2.00±0.57 ^e	3.00±0.00 ^{de}	30.00
<i>Z. mauratania</i>	20	2.66±0.66 ^{de}	4.00±0.57 ^{cde}	5.66±0.66 ^{cd}	6.66±0.88 ^{bc}	66.66
	10	2.33±0.66 ^{def}	3.66±0.88 ^{efgh}	5.00±1.52 ^{cde}	5.33±1.66 ^{bcd}	53.33
	6	1.33±0.88 ^{ef}	1.66±0.66 ^{ghi}	3.66±0.66 ^{cde}	3.66±0.66 ^{cde}	36.66
	2	1.0±0.53 ^{ef}	1.66±0.88 ^{ghi}	2.00±1.15 ^e	3.33±0.88 ^{de}	33.33
Cypermethrin	0.05	9.67±0.33 ^a	10.00±0.00 ^a	10.00±0.00 ^a	10.00±0.00 ^a	100.00
Control	0.00	1.33±0.33 ^{ef}	1.33±0.33 ^{hi}	1.33±0.35 ^e	2.00±0.57 ^e	20.00

Means with the same super script along the column showed no significant difference at p<0.05% using Duncan’s multiple rangetest.

5.0 Conclusion

The study demonstrated the toxicidal activity of five aqueous plant extracts against *D. maculatus* larvae. The aqueous extracts of *O. gratisimum* and *P. guineense* were found more effective in the control of *D. maculatus* larval infestation on stored dried fish compared with others tested plants extracts. The finding revealed the effectiveness of five tested plants in control of larvae of *D. maculatus* infesting dried fish and this can be an alternative to synthetic insecticides.

6.0 Recommendations

The finding this study revealed that all the tested plans extracts could be used in prevention and control of *D. maculatus* infestation on dred fish .Therefore,

7.0 References

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